

CURRENT ISSUES OF INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY RIGHTS PROTECTION (COPYRIGHT AND ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE TECHNOLOGIES)

Jaksilikov Aydos Kamiljan uli

Berdakh KSU, Faculty of Law, 1st year bachelor's
student, majoring in "Jurisprudence"

ORCID: 0009-0008-8467-3902

e-mail: aydos8571gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20233314>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 12th May 2026

Accepted: 14th May 2026

Online: 16th May 2026

KEYWORDS

intellectual property rights, copyright, artificial intelligence, works created by AI, human creative work, Copyright Law of Uzbekistan, Civil Code.

ABSTRACT

This thesis analyzes the current issues of intellectual property rights protection, in particular, the relationship between copyright and artificial intelligence technologies. The main purpose of the study is to study the legal status of works created by AI based on the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Civil Code and the Law "On Copyright and Related Rights" and to assess the effectiveness of the mechanisms for their protection. In the study, I analyzed Article 53 of the Constitution, Section IV of the Civil Code, Articles 3 and 8 of the Copyright Law, and Presidential Decree No. PQ-221. The results show that under Uzbek law, copyright applies only to works created by human creative labor. Materials created by pure AI, since they do not have direct creative contribution from humans, are not protected by copyright and are considered public property. If a person edits the result of AI or adds his own opinion, only that part can be protected. In my opinion, this situation creates a huge legal gap. In conclusion, I suggest the need to improve national legislation, develop clear criteria for human-AI collaborative works, and take into account international experience.

Today, artificial intelligence technologies are developing very rapidly. Programs such as ChatGPT and Midjourney can write text, draw pictures, or create music in a matter of seconds. This situation interested me very much, because intellectual property rights are mainly based on a person's own creative work, ideas, and abilities. Therefore, in this thesis, I wanted to study the legal status of works created by AI in the legislation of Uzbekistan, and whether they can be protected or not. First of all, Article 53 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan stipulates that freedom of scientific, technical, and artistic creativity is guaranteed and intellectual property is protected by law. This norm creates the main constitutional basis for encouraging and protecting any creative activity. Section IV of the Civil Code details intellectual property objects, their legal nature, and the general procedure for protection. This section regulates intellectual property in civil legal relations. In my opinion, the most important document is the Law "On Copyright and Related Rights". In its Article 3,

the author is understood as a natural person who has created a work through his creative work. That is, copyright is related only to the personal creative contribution of a person. Article 8 clearly states that results obtained with the help of electronic computers, without direct human creative activity, are not considered objects of copyright. For example, if I simply give AI the prompt “draw a beautiful mountain landscape” and it produces a finished picture, this picture is not protected by copyright and is considered public property. In my personal opinion, this rule is correct in principle. Because copyright should reflect a person’s own thoughts, feelings, and creative work. If only a machine works, then there will be no real creativity. But in life, situations are different. For example, if a human deeply edits the result created by AI, adds his own ideas, changes the content or adds new elements, then I think only this human part should be protected. However, in such cases, the current laws do not have a mechanism to clearly distinguish which part of the work belongs to the human and which part belongs to the AI. This situation, in my opinion, creates a huge legal gap. Because on the one hand, the rights of creators are not sufficiently protected, and on the other hand, uncertainties arise in the development of AI technologies.

¹The Resolution of our President No. PQ-221 of April 26, 2022 “On Additional Measures for the Further Development of the Intellectual Property Sector” sets out an important strategy for protecting intellectual property and encouraging innovation. This document is aimed at improving the national system. Also, ²Article 13 of the Law “On Competition” (No. ORQ-850, 2023) prohibits unfair competition. It defines unfair competition as the unfair use of intellectual property objects of other persons, including works created using AI. In my opinion, this norm is very relevant today. Because many people can use AI-created works as their own, damaging the reputation of others or gaining an unfair advantage in the market. During my research, I realized that existing laws do not fully cover the new possibilities of artificial intelligence. This legal gap could pose a problem for both creators and technology developers in the future. My personal position is that the principle of human authorship should remain fundamental and unchanging. But when humans and AI work together, it is time to develop clear criteria for determining what part of a work is a human creative contribution. For example, indicators such as the complexity of the prompt, the amount of editing, the level of new ideas and changes made by humans can be set.

The best way for Uzbekistan is to make appropriate amendments to the Law "On Copyright and Related Rights" within the framework of PQ-221 and introduce mechanisms to separately regulate works related to AI. This will both protect human creativity and ensure that technological progress does not stop.

In conclusion, the protection of intellectual property rights requires maintaining the centrality of human creativity in the era of artificial intelligence technologies. Through this

¹ Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 26, 2022 No. PQ-221 “On Additional Measures for the Further Development of the Intellectual Property Sector”. <http://lex.uz/uz/docs/-5987120>

² Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Competition” (No. O'PYK-850, 03.07.2023).

<http://lex.uz/uz/docs/-6518381>

study, I have analyzed existing laws, identified legal gaps, and made my own proposals. In the future, it is very important to study this topic in more depth and improve national legislation, taking into account international experience. I believe that this will lead not only individual creators, but also society as a whole towards innovation and creativity..

List of used literature:

1. Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 01.05.2023 (Article 53).
2. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Copyright and Related Rights” (No. O'PYK-42, 2006, as amended).a
3. Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 01.03.1997 (Part IV, Articles 1031–1111).
4. Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 26, 2022 No. PQ-221 “On Additional Measures for the Further Development of the Intellectual Property Sector”.
5. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Competition” (No. O'PYK-850, 03.07.2023).

